

STRUCTURAL-FUNCTIONAL APPROACHES TO IMPROVING THE ETHNO- PEDAGOGICAL CULTURE OF THE FUTURE MUSIC TEACHER

Tukhtasinov Abror Rustamovich

Doctoral student of Namangan state university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10253851>

Annotation: This article contains methods, various pedagogical conditions, and recommendations for improving the ethnopedagogical culture of future music teachers. The use of the subject of "Uzbek folk music" and the forms of the functional approach to improving the pedagogical culture of future music teachers were discussed.

Keywords: music, pedagogy, ethnopedagogy, education, music creation, criterion, method, competition, festival, motive, cognitive.

Music is a mirror of the nation's soul, its spiritual world, an interpreter of its emotions, which means its national identity. It is not only aesthetic education, but also moral, spiritual, spiritual, religious and theological education. Any nation, any nation, willy-nilly needs music in order to achieve its economic well-being. The unprecedented pleasant power of music to affect the human mind and emotions is due to its specific nature, which is in harmony with mental processes. In the content of musical works, artistic ideas are presented in a generalized way, and the mutual relations of images are formed in processes such as mutual comparison, conflict, and development. According to the characteristics of this process, its content will have different - epic, dramatic, lyrical characters. Among these, the inner world of a person is very close to the "inner" nature of music, which expresses his mental states. It is not for nothing that music is called the art of muse (angels) in Greek.

The heritage of Uzbek national music culture is extremely rich and colorful, and its roots go back to the ancient times of our ancestors. This national cultural heritage, as an inseparable, identity value of our nation, appeared on the basis of the creativity of the population's social life and continues to this day. The creation of the traditions of folk art, flourishing over time, from the initial stages of the development of artistic thinking to the development of national-spiritual culture in different periods, based on its high examples, not only in educating the spiritual and spiritual culture of the population, but also it is also used as the main tool in the education of manners and moral qualities.

Decisions made by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on February 2, 2022 "On additional measures for the further development of the sphere of culture and art" are for the spiritual and ideological life of our country today's globalization, "mass Those who signed the decision, which is important in a time of increased attacks on "culture", are in front of all music, art and culture workers, students of continuing education institutions, as well as professors, teachers, scientists, students of higher education institutions. imposes extremely great responsibility and demands.[1]

Undoubtedly, as stated in this decision, it is necessary to increase the level of providing cultural recreation services for all layers of the population, including the people aged seven to seventy who live in remote and remote areas of our country, and even the theater of art, circus and other types of mass-cultural and concert viewing events systematically and permanently, discovering talents in the field of music, culture and art among the population, finding them, supporting them, encouraging them encouragement, it is no secret that some educational institutions and their information-resource centers lack textbooks, educational

and methodical manuals, sheet music collections, educational-methodical literature and, most importantly, ethno-pedagogical knowledge of the future music teacher. It is not difficult to notice that the methodology of culture is aimed at the holistic system of provision, and that it is aimed at the solution of the actual problems, the implementation of which is important in this regard. There is also a symbolic meaning in the implementation of the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 in accordance with the state program on the implementation of the "Year of glorifying human dignity and active neighborhood". "Folkmusic" programs of educating the young generation growing up in the world education system on the basis of national musical traditions have been applied to the educational process. Music education dedicated to the organization of group singing of national songs, folklore lessons in the music education system of the Netherlands, Romania, Czech Republic, Russia, Estonia, Lithuania, Bulgaria, Poland, Uruguay, qualified in music education within the Bologna teaching system. Systematic work is being carried out on implementation of large-scale projects on the use of non-traditional forms and methods of personnel training, the study of the ethno-pedagogical culture system. Germany puts forward the idea of "Education of children on the basis of folklore examples, religious and spiritual music, German classical works" as the main direction of musical pedagogy. They believe that it is appropriate to use it for the purpose of music therapy, not for teaching music.

Action strategy for the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan "further improving the continuous education system, increasing the possibilities of quality educational services, continuing the policy of training highly qualified personnel in line with the modern needs of the labor market, making children spend their free time meaningfully, making them enjoy music and construction of children's music and art schools in order to attract them to art, to pay serious attention to the issues of reconstruction of the existing ones and their rational use" were defined as priority tasks. As an integral part of the decision, starting from the 2022/2023 academic year, students in educational institutions should improve their musical knowledge, skills, and competences, instilling in their hearts national spirituality, love and feelings for culture through music. important tasks were set, such as forming them, educating them on this basis, sending the growing young generation to the profession through musical education. It's not for nothing. If we look at the musical education of the countries of the world, improvement of personnel training system based on national musical traditions in the world's leading educational institutions; choir team, orchestra of young violinists, development of singing performance; strengthening of national customs based on folklore sayings; aims to conduct musical education on the basis of folk singing and musical instrument performance, to develop the cultural and aesthetic outlook of students, and to raise young people who are loyal to universal values. [2]

In this regard, in the text of the decision, various forms of formation of national singing works and performance skills on musical instruments in general secondary schools, children's music and art schools, secondary special, professional and higher educational institutions and cultural centers. According to the conditions, a number of tasks to be performed during 2022-2026 have been defined, starting from the formation of practical skills of students and even the training of pedagogues and professors and employees of culture, art, and theater. includes a wide range of tasks, such as re-training, training, and participation of talented young people in national and international competitions and festivals. The most important issues such as

the mechanisms of implementation of these tasks, financial costs, their addresses, and the appropriate payment of labor have been solved in each item. It is clear from this that this decision was not made just in name. As a result, the professional potential of the participants will change, and the number of qualified specialists will be employed.

In a word, all educational institutions, culture, art, theater centers, official Leaders should not limit themselves to fulfilling the tasks defined in this decision, but first of all, they should develop the existing sector, eliminate the problems that have accumulated and are waiting for their solution, and when the time comes, they should further increase the value and scope of this decision based on the “roadmaps”.

It should not be forgotten that the essence of music, art, and culture is a unity of personal, national and universal artistic values, in which spiritual freshness, speed, social thought and experiences typical of a certain nation, society and historical period are summarized. is expressed. Their forms meet the spiritual and educational requirements of each era, and at the same time, they are common to many aspects of human activity (certain collective activities, ethical and aesthetic interaction of people, communication processes). In this regard, the role of music as a means of forming a person’s moral and aesthetic taste, developing his emotional feelings, and developing his creative abilities is very important today.

Currently, in improving the ethnopedagogical culture of the future music teacher, it is recognized as a complex multifaceted system that includes his worldview positions, value orientations, personal characteristics, mastered pedagogical experience and the level of his initiation into the educational environment. received. It is formed under the influence of various factors of social, primarily professional, reality at all stages of the professional development of a future music teacher, but its main basis is laid in the process of training a future specialist in the field of pedagogy in higher educational institutions. These conceptual relationships do not lose their importance when it comes to improving the ethno-pedagogical culture of the future music teacher.

In this dissertation, on the basis of an active approach, while revealing the content and essence of the development of the professional culture of the future music teacher, the entire social life of the performer from the point of view of the subject was considered as a method of development, comparison, comparison and example. [3]

In the systematic approach, we followed the opinion that it is necessary to consider all pedagogical events as a kind of unique educational system. Based on this position, we see the possibility of solving the problem of our research, taking into account the need to systematically organize the professional training of future music teachers in the field of musical instruments and performing arts, to improve their professional and ethnopedagogical culture as music teachers. we said “Pedagogical system” makes it possible to understand a certain set of interrelated tools, methods, processes necessary to create a purposeful and intentional pedagogical effect, improving the student’s ethno-pedagogical culture. [4] The systematic approach made it possible to establish internal and external relations of the process of improving the ethnopedagogical culture of the future music teacher, where the content is determined by the given goal and shows that the achievement of the given result is related to the created conditions.

The use of an integrative approach is related to the need to reflect the features of the professional activity of improving the ethno-pedagogical culture of the future music teacher during the design process. Its implementation ensures the interdependence of professional-creative, educational-pedagogical activities in the single process of musical literacy and the musical and singing performance skills of undergraduate students, which provides students with a number of professionally important opens wide opportunities for the formation of qualities. In particular, this approach showed the importance of mastering musical instruments and performance skills as a necessary element of ethnopedagogical and professional culture of a future music teacher. Simultaneous use of different forms of activity helped to develop their integral skills and abilities. In this case - constructive (logical adjustment of the music lesson in the unity of organizational and instrumental and singing activities), informational (ability to use various tools), informational resources in the implementation of pedagogical activities, communicative (implementation of pedagogical interaction using performance skills increase). It was determined that the subject-oriented pedagogical interaction of students' educational activity management was used by the future music teacher in solving specially organized educational tasks of various complexity and problems. A high degree of subjectivity inherent in the implementation of activities as an artistic and creative activity, as well as the presence of natural inclinations and the requirements for the development of special abilities for its implementation served as the basis for understanding the improvement of professional and ethno-pedagogical culture.

In the process of improving the ethno-pedagogical culture of future music teachers, it is impossible to separate from the tasks of personal development. Therefore, the decisive factor in choosing such an approach is "...creating conditions for self-development of a well-rounded, morally perfect, socially active, professional person based on ancestral values, traditions and traditions". Improvement of the required quality in students showed that their individual professional, personal and ethno-pedagogical development depends on a higher level of professional culture than a certain level of musical and singing performance training. [5] The defined trajectory of the process is that the subject content of musical-theoretical subjects mastered by students is recognized by them as professional and personal values at the same time (music is a means of developing the student's personality and a means of developing one's own personality). Ethno-pedagogical spiritual enrichment of the student, as an opportunity for professional creativity, knowing the world and themselves in it as a means of artistic communication and self-expression), as a result of which the educational process acquires a personal meaning for them.

The choice of a competition-based approach was determined by the need to coordinate the educational process with modern educational requirements. The main idea of this approach is that "the main result of education is not individual knowledge, skills and abilities, but the ability and readiness of a person to work effectively and efficiently in various socially significant situations. In this regard the dominant idea is not only to "increase the volume" of knowledge, but also to have versatile experience in activities. One of the main aspects of any activity is the ability to predict the outcome of actions. Therefore, in the implementation of the competence-based approach in teacher education, it is necessary not only to "form the model conditions of pedagogical work, but also to develop the research activity of students.

When designing the methodology process for improving the ethnopedagogical culture of the future music teacher, it is intended to overcome its highly specialized direction in favor of developing skills for a wide range of activities that will ensure the successful implementation of multi-vector professional activities. [6]The need to establish a connection between the components of the ethnopedagogical culture of future music teachers and the organization of activities for its improvement, incorporating general cultural, psychological-pedagogical, musical and musical performance aspects based on a cultural approach.

From the point of view of this approach, education is a cultural process that takes place in a culturally appropriate educational environment and is aimed at improving the social (cultural) experience of future music teachers, including knowledge, methods of activity, experience of creative activity, students It should be noted that the experience acquired by a person in the educational process is the point of intersection of competence-based and cultural approaches in terms of experience, emotional and value relations.

However, if the competence-based approach is aimed at the mastery of certain competencies by students as a basis for acting in various professional situations, the cultural approach assumes the development of all important forces of the individual, which forms a structure that includes these abilities. A certain type of ethno-pedagogical activity, knowledge, skills, ability to implement it, depends on the person's orientation to this activity. Implementation of the cultural studies approach in the modeled process creates a culturally consistent educational environment that contributes to the improvement of the ethnopedagogical culture of the future music teacher.

References:

1. Abdullaeva Q. M. Methodological basis of formation of professional knowledge and skills of future teachers in teaching special subjects: Dis: ped. scientific name - Tashkent, 2006. P. 182.
2. Muslimov N. A. Professional formation of future vocational education teachers. Tashkent. Science. 2004.
3. Panjiev K. B. Uzbek folk singing art. Study guide. Tashkent. 2022. - P. 210.
4. Panjiev K.B. Improvement of professional training of future music teachers by means of Uzbek folk singers. Monograph. T.: 2022.-P. 204.
5. Kholikov A. A. Pedagogical skills. Monograph. Tashkent. Economy and finance. 2011. - P. 418.
6. Rakhimov B. Kh. Formation of professional and cultural relations in future teachers: Diss. ped. science. tnom. - Tashkent. 2002. - P. 161.